

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION ON RP-HPLC FOR ASSAY OF BULK AND FORMULATION OF CARMUSTINE

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I. ABSTRACT: -

The isocratic RP-HPLC was used for method development of carmustine and simultaneous estimation of carmustine by using 4.6 mm X 250mm, 5- μ m Shim-Pack solar (C18) column. Mobile phase was used contained a combination of Acetonitrile, water & buffer at the ratio of 4:5:1 respectively, flow rate was 1.0 ml min⁻¹ with a total run time of 20 minutes, column temperature was 37°C, observation was carried out at 254 nm using photo diode-array detector. Retention time found to be 13.270 & 13.10 minutes for pure carmustine and carmustine nanosuspension respectively and area for pure carmustine drug and carmustine nanosuspension was found to be

287059 & 287056 respectively. And linear regression coefficient was found to be 0.9972. Assay method was established for quantitative estimation of Carmustine from bulk drug & formulation.

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II. KEYWORDS: -

RP-HPLC- Reverse Phased-High Performance Liquid Chromatography

BiCNU- Bischloroethylnitrosourea.

RSD- Relative Standard Deviation

ACN- Acetonitrile

PDA- Photo-Diode

III. INTRODUCTION: -

Carmustine is an alkylating agent which is intended for the treatment of malignancies, brain tumors and multiple myeloma. Carmustine is one among the nitrosourea derivative. It is used as a chemotherapeutic agent which is also given in combination with alternative approved anticancer agents in treatment of tumors, Hodgkin's disease, and non-Hodgkin's, multiple myeloma. HPLC is high performance liquid chromatography, it is a method in analytical chemistry which is used to isolate, detect, and quantify element from pharmaceutical bulk and formulation. HPLC depend on on pump to move a controlled liquid i.e., mobile phase and a sample mixture through a analytical column which is stuffed with adsorbent, which leads to the separation of components from the sample. The key element of the column is the adsorbent, is usually a granular material made from solid particles of silica gel having particle size ranging from 2–50 μm . The sample mixture containing componenets are separated from each other due to their relative affinity towards adsorbent particles i.e., stationary phase. The mobile phase used is typically a combination of solvents. (e.g., ACN, water or methanol or buffer). Composition of mobile phase and temperature plays a significant role in the separation of sample in the analytical column. The current method was

developed and validated for estimation of carmustine from pharmaceutical bulk and formulation. This method can be used for the determination of percent of carmustine from commercially available bulk and formulation.

IV. OBJECTIVES

- To study chromatogram of standard carmustine
- To study chromatogram of carmustine in acid, alkaline and thermal degradation

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In it we study the various steps that are generally adopted by a researcher in studying his research problem along with the logic behind them. It is necessary for the researcher to know not only the research methods/techniques but also the methodology. In order to apply the analytical and descriptive methods to the research a close reading and detailed analysis of secondary sources available. It is significant to get other perceptions to elaborate the textual analysis and this would need close reading analysis of few secondary materials.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL WORK: -

1.1. MATERIAL AND REAGENTS: -

Carmustine was made available as Gift sample from Emcure Pvt. Ltd. Pune. The prepared mobile phase was the combination of acetonitrile, water and sodium phosphate buffer (Mixed) PH 7 at a ratio of 4:5:1 respectively. And then the mobile phase was subjected in ultrasonicator and sonicated for 10 minutes then it was filtered.

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1.2. INITIAL CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS: -

"Table 1 Chromatographic Conditions"

1	Column	4.6 mm X 250mm, 5- μ m Shim-Pack solar (C18)
2	Column temperature	37°C
3	Detector	Photo-Diode array (PDA)
4	Flow rate	1.0 ml/min
5	Pump mode	Isocratic
6	Injection volume	20 μ l
7	Run time	20 min
8	Mobile phase	ACN, water and Phosphate buffer (Mixed) PH 7 (40:50:10)

1.3. PREPARATION OF BUFFER: -

The buffer of PH 7.0 (Mixed) was prepared by dissolving 0.50 gm of anhydrous sodium phosphate dibasic dihydrate and 0.301 gm of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000 ml of water.

1.4. MOBILE PHASE: -

The mobile phase was made by taking ACN, water & buffer PH 7.0. at concentration of 40, 50 & 10 ml respectively & after that sonicated in the ultra sonicator for 10 minutes.

1.5. PREPARATION OF STANDARD STOCK SOLUTION (PURE CARMUSTINE): -

The standard stock solution was developed by introducing the standard pure carmustine drug in solvent containing mobile phase. A 10mg sample of carmustine standard accurately weighed, transferred in a 100ml (0.1

mg/ml OR 100 µg/ml) volumetric flask containing mobile phase. Further 1.0 ml was taken and transferred in a 10ml volumetric flask, and diluted with the mobile phase (10 µg/ml).

1.6. PREPARATION OF SAMPLE (STOCK) SOLUTION: -

Formulation of carmustine (nano-suspension) containing 5mg carmustine in 15ml of solvent base. Further 1ml solution was taken and shifted in separate 50ml capacity volumetric flask and final concentration was maintained at 0.33/ml i.e., 333 µg/ml. Again 33 ml of Mobile phase is added in the above and the ultimate concentration of stock solution becomes 10 µg/ml.

VII. RESULT: - METHOD DEVELOPMENT: -

Appropriate selection of the method based on the nature of the sample. From the literature survey and with the knowledge of properties of the selected drug, 4.6 mm X 250mm, 5-µm Shim-Pack solar (C18) column was tried & chosen as stationary phase and mobile phase with different compositions such as acetonitrile, water was used. The separations were not observed, so the combination of phosphate buffer, acetonitrile & water was finalized. The phosphate buffer tried at different pH 8.0 to pH 5.5. It was observed that phosphate buffer with pH-7.0 good retention. A typical chromatogram for standard and formulation and Formulation of Nano-suspension of carmustine was shown in figure 1 & 2. The retention time of pure drug and formulation of carmustine was found to be 13.20 min & 13.10 min respectively with the area of standard pure carmustine and carmustine nanosuspension was found to be 287059 & 287056 respectively.

“Figure 1 Chromatogram of Standard Carmustine (Pure Drug).”

“Figure 2 Chromatogram of Carmustine Formulation (Nano- Suspension)”

VIII. METHOD VALIDATION: -

SYSTEM SELECTIVITY: -The system selectivity refers to an ability of system to separate two analytes. This study was performed under acidic, basic and thermal degradation. The developed RP-HPLC method was performed in presence of 0.1 N HCL for acidic degradation (shown in Fig.3), 0.2 N NaOH for basic degradation (shown in fig.4) and 40 °C for thermal degradation (Fig.5) the respected substance studies were carried out for stress samples against carmustine standard and percent purity, percent degraded products were calculated.

“Figure 3 Chromatogram of carmustine in acid degradation”

“Figure 4 Chromatogram of carmustine in alkaline degradation”

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“Figure 5 Chromatogram of carmustine in thermal degradation”

1.1. SPECIFICITY: -

The system specificity refers to the ability of system to distinguish between analyte and components present in carmustine sample. It was determined by injecting blank, placebo, standard and sample and there is no interference of placebo with standard and sample of carmustine hence the developed method was found to be specific, and it show respectable retention time 13.2 for standard and 13.10 minutes for sample of carmustine.

1.2. LINEARITY: -

Linearity study was performed by preparing 5 different concentrations viz. 0, 5, 15, 20 and 25 µg/ml. Five different concentrations were injected and the linearity range was determined. As shown in Fig. 7 and table 2. The linearity range of carmustine was found to be 0 µg/ml -30µg/ml.

“Figure 6 Linearity curve Carmustine VS Peak area”

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“Table 2 Linearity Result”

SR.NO	CONCENTRATION (µg/ml)	AREA
1	0	0
2	5	103529
3	10	287059
4	15	430588
5	20	574118
6	25	717253

1.3. ACCURACY: -

Accuracy is the closeness of result to the accurate value. And it was determined by recovery experiments by adding known concentration of standard solution to the sample solution and it was carried out at 8 µg/ml, 10 µg/ml and 12 µg/ml. and sample solution concentration maintained at 10 µg/ml. The percentage recovery for carmustine was calculated and reported

"Table 3 Accuracy Result"

SR.NO	PERCENT LEVEL (%)	CON. OF FORMULATION (µg/ml)	PURE DRUG CON. (µg/ml)	PERCENT RECOVERY (%)	(%) MEAN RECOVERY	±SD	(%) RSD
1	80	10	8	99.04	99.03	0.4150	0.4190
	80	10	8	99.45			
	80	10	8	98.62			
2	100	10	10	99.47	99.94	0.5200	0.5203
	100	10	10	100.5			
	100	10	10	99.86			
3	120	10	12	99.87	99.48	0.52	0.5227
	120	10	12	99.25			
	120	10	12	99.33			

CON.: Concentration, SD: Standard Deviation, RSD: Relative Standard Deviation

1.4. PRECISION: -

The method precision was performed to check closeness of results obtained with the same sample i.e., carmustine and it was determined and following results was obtained.

"Table 4 Repeatability Method Precision"

SR.NO	SAMPLE	PERCENT CARMUSTINE
1	1	99.9
2	2	99.6
3	3	99.5
4	4	99.1
5	5	99.8

6	6	99.2
MEAN		99.5
% RSD		0.32090

% RSD: Relative Standard Deviation

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1.5. ROBUSTNESS: -

Robustness is the analytical process which remains unaffected by small or cautious change in system parameters. The robustness was carried out by altering flow rate 0.8ml/min and 1.2 ml/min. and by altering column temperature at 34°C and 40°C.

“Table 5 Robustness Result”

SR.NO	SYSTEM PARAMETERS	ALTERATION	RETENTION TIME(Min.)	THEROTICAL PLATES	AREA
1	FLOW RATE	0.8 mlmin ⁻¹	14.52 min	10567	287758
		1.2 mlmin ⁻¹	12.4 min	9322	262578
2	COLUMN TEMPERATURE	34°C	15.010 min	11254	287068
		40°C	12.72 min	9257	275239

Min.: Minutes

1.6. RUGGEDNESS: -

The ruggedness refers to the degree of reproducibility of test results which remains unchanged under conditions like different instruments and analyst. The ruggedness study was carried out by analysing six assay samples of carmustine formulation. And for present method % recovery and SD were calculated and reported.

“Table 6 Ruggedness Result”

SR.NO	CONCENTRATION OF FORMULATION (µg/mL)	PURE DRUG CON. (µg/mL)	ANALYST 1		ANALYST 2	
			% MEAN RECOVERY	±SD	% MEAN RECOVERY	±SD
1	10 µg/mL	5 µg/mL	99.27	0.45	99.28	0.55

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Standard Deviation, CON.: Concentration

IX. CONCLUSION: -

The current assay method was established which aimed at quantitative estimation of carmustine from pure carmustine and pharmaceutical dosage form. The established method was found to be stability indicating. The developed method was validated and found to be rapid, highly precise, accurate, specific. The developed method can be used for assessment percent of carmustine from pharmaceutical and bulk dosage form. Selection of buffer and mobile phase composition played a significant role on the separation selectivity. Final optimization was accomplished by altering temperature, flow rate as well as type and composition of mobile phase. The selected mobile phase at a concentration of 40:50:10 of ACN: Water: Buffer respectively was found to be effective and shows good retention time at 13.27 minutes for pure carmustine and 13.10 minutes for carmustine formulation. And area 287059 for pure carmustine and 287056 for carmustine formulation. Linear regression coefficient was found NMT 0.9972.

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